

Research Article

Survival Outcomes and Prognostic Factors in Non-Metastatic Nasopharyngeal Cancer Treated with Conventional Radiotherapy in Cameroon: A 6-Year Retrospective Cohort Study in Douala

Survie et Facteurs Pronostiques du Cancer du Nasopharynx Non Métastatique Traité par Radiothérapie Conventionnelle au Cameroun : Une Étude de Cohorte Rétrospective de 6 Ans à Douala

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18964388>

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Non-metastatic nasopharyngeal cancer is a public health issue in Cameroon, where access to modern radiotherapy is limited. Douala General Hospital operates the country's only public 2D radiotherapy machine. This study aimed to analyze overall survival (OS) and recurrence-free survival (RFS) in patients treated under these constraints and identify prognostic factors. **Methods.** This retrospective cross-sectional study included all patients with histologically confirmed non-metastatic nasopharyngeal cancer (stages I-IVA, AJCC 8th) treated with radiotherapy at Douala General Hospital from 2017 to 2022. Data were collected from medical records and telephone interviews. Survival was analyzed using Kaplan-Meier method and Cox regression. **Results.** Among 75 patients, mean age was 42.4±16.2 years, with male predominance (62.7%). Stage III disease was most common (57.3%), followed by stage IVA (20%). Nearly all patients (96%) received concurrent chemoradiation with 60-66 Gy delivered over 59.1±11.5 days. Five-year OS and RFS were 5% and 4%, respectively. Median OS was 25 months; median RFS was 23 months. In multivariate analysis, age >65 years was independently associated with poor RFS (HR=14.7; 95%CI 5.04-42.6; p<0.001), while age 18-35 years was associated with better OS (HR=0.25; 95%CI 0.08-0.79; p=0.018). **Conclusion.** Survival rates for non-metastatic nasopharyngeal cancer in Cameroon are dramatically below international standards, reflecting late diagnosis and limitations of 2D Cobalt-60 radiotherapy. Urgent modernization to intensity-modulated radiotherapy (IMRT) and intensified early detection efforts are essential.

RESUME

Introduction. Le cancer du nasopharynx non métastatique est un problème de santé publique au Cameroun, où l'accès à la radiothérapie moderne est limité. L'Hôpital Général de Douala dispose de la seule machine publique de radiothérapie 2D du pays. Cette étude a visé à analyser la survie globale (SG) et la survie sans récidive (SSR) des patients traités sous ces contraintes et à identifier les facteurs pronostiques. **Méthodologie.** Une étude rétrospective transversale a inclus tous les patients atteints d'un cancer du nasopharynx non métastatique (stades I-IVA, AJCC 8e) histologiquement prouvé, traités par radiothérapie à l'Hôpital Général de Douala de 2017 à 2022. Les données ont été recueillies à partir des dossiers médicaux et d'entretiens téléphoniques. La survie a été analysée par la méthode de Kaplan-Meier et la régression de Cox. **Résultats.** Sur 75 patients, l'âge moyen était de 42,4±16,2 ans, avec une prédominance masculine (62,7 %). Le stade III était le plus fréquent (57,3 %), suivi du stade IVA (20 %). La quasi-totalité des patients (96 %) ont reçu une radiochimiothérapie concomitante avec une dose de 60-66 Gy délivrée en 59,1±11,5 jours. La SG et la SSR à 5 ans étaient respectivement de 5 % et 4 %. La SG médiane était de 25 mois ; la SSR médiane de 23 mois. En analyse multivariée, l'âge >65 ans était indépendamment associé à une mauvaise SSR (HR=14,7 ; IC95 % 5,04-42,6 ; p<0,001), tandis que l'âge 18-35 ans était associé à une meilleure SG (HR=0,25 ; IC95 % 0,08-0,79 ; p=0,018). **Conclusion.** Les taux de survie pour le cancer du nasopharynx non métastatique au Cameroun sont dramatiquement inférieurs aux standards internationaux, reflétant un diagnostic tardif et les limites de la radiothérapie 2D au Cobalt-60. Une modernisation urgente vers la radiothérapie conformationnelle avec modulation d'intensité (RCMI) et des efforts nationaux de détection précoce sont essentiels.

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Key words : Cancer, nasopharynx, 2D radiotherapy, Cobalt 60, survival, Cameroon, Douala General Hospital, chemo radiation

Mots clés: Cancer, nasopharynx, radiothérapie 2D, cobalt 60, survie, Cameroun, Hôpital général de Douala, chimioradiothérapie

Article history

Submitted: 16 January 2026
Revisions requested: 3 March 2026
Accepted: 22 March 2026
Published: 25 March 2026

HIGHLIGHTS FOR READERS IN A HURRY

What is already known on this topic. Nasopharyngeal cancer is radiosensitive, and with modern intensity-modulated radiotherapy (IMRT) combined with chemotherapy, 5-year survival rates exceed 80% in early stages. Access to such technology is limited in sub-Saharan Africa.

The question this study addressed. This study evaluated overall and recurrence-free survival in 75 patients with non-metastatic nasopharyngeal cancer treated with 2D conventional radiotherapy at the only public radiotherapy center in Cameroon between 2017 and 2022.

What this study adds to our knowledge. It reveals alarmingly low 5-year survival rates: 5% overall and 4% recurrence-free. Most patients (77.3%) were diagnosed at locally advanced stages (III-IVA). Age >65 years was the strongest independent predictor of poor outcome (HR=14.7), while patients aged 18-45 fared better. Treatment duration exceeded 60 days in 50.7% of cases.

How this is relevant to clinical practice, policy or further research. These findings underscore the urgent need to modernize Cameroon's radiotherapy infrastructure to IMRT and establish national early detection programs. They also highlight the importance of minimizing treatment interruptions. A national cancer registry and referral network are essential.

INTRODUCTION

Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) is a malignant epithelial tumour whose complex aetiology involves genetic, environmental and infectious factors (notably the Epstein-Barr virus) [1]. In 2022, the Global Cancer Observatory (GCO) estimated the global incidence of this cancer at 1.3% and the associated mortality at 0.77% [2]. The geographical distribution of NPC is notably heterogeneous, defining three distinct risk areas: a high-endemicity area in Southeast Asia (30 to 80/100,000 inhabitants/year), an intermediate-risk area in the Mediterranean basin (2 to 3/100,000 inhabitants/year), and a low-risk area covering Europe and North America (0.5 to 2/100,000 inhabitants/year) [3]. In sub-Saharan Africa, and specifically in Cameroon, NPC represents a significant oncological entity. In 2022, it ranked 11th among the most common cancers in the country, with an estimated prevalence of 1.9% [2]. It is also the most common neoplasm in the ear, nose and throat (ENT) area, sometimes accounting for more than a fifth of reported ENT cancer cases [4]. The diagnosis of NPC requires a multidisciplinary approach. However, the lack of specialised resources in certain regions of low- and middle-income countries often leads to late diagnosis.

In Cameroon, previous studies confirm that NSCLC is mainly diagnosed at locally advanced stages (stages III and IV) [5; 6]. Curative treatment of non-metastatic NSCLC is mainly based on radiotherapy. For locally advanced stages, the standard treatment combines external radiotherapy with concomitant chemotherapy (CCT). Induction chemotherapy may precede CRT, particularly in the presence of T4 tumours and/or extensive lymph node involvement [7]. Radiotherapy of

the head and neck region is typically associated with acute and late toxicities. These side effects, such as radiodermatitis, mucositis, xerostomia, ageusia, dysphagia, odynophagia, etc., depend on the dose and irradiation technique [6; 8]. Older two-dimensional/three-dimensional (2D/3D) radiotherapy techniques were associated with an increased frequency and severity of these toxicities [9].

Since the 1990s, technological advances in radiotherapy, particularly the advent of intensity-modulated radiotherapy (IMRT), have led to significant improvements in dose distribution. These modern techniques are associated with better local control of the disease and a notable reduction in acute and late side effects [9]. A meta-analysis conducted by Zhang et al. demonstrated the advantage of IMRT techniques over older techniques (2D/3D), particularly in terms of 5-year overall survival (OR=1.51; 95% CI 1.23-1.87; p=0.0001) and reduction in late toxicities [9]. As a result, IMRT is now the standard technique recommended by learned societies for the curative treatment of non-metastatic nasopharyngeal cancer [7].

In Cameroon, radiotherapy facilities are stagnating. In 1989, Douala General Hospital (HGD) and Yaoundé General Hospital (HGY) each had a radiotherapy department equipped with a 2D radiotherapy machine and a brachytherapy machine. Currently, only the HGD radiotherapy department remains operational with 2D equipment (Cobalt 60), as the HGY department has closed. Although a private centre (Cameroon Oncology Centre) introduced a linear accelerator (3D/IMRT) into the country in 2019, access to this cutting-edge technology is severely limited for the majority of patients due to the socio-economic context and the lack of a structured social security system. The radiotherapy department at the HGD therefore remains the main centre for the treatment of non-metastatic stages of this disease. A study conducted by Mouelle et al. in 1996, based on 2D treatment at the HGD, had already revealed a low 5-year survival rate (29%) compared to developed countries [6]. Considering the evolution of international treatment recommendations for cavum cancer and the continued use of outdated radiotherapy technology at the HGD, it seems essential to reassess the prognosis of patients treated at this institution.

The objective of this study is therefore to analyse the overall survival and recurrence-free survival of patients with non-metastatic nasopharyngeal carcinoma treated with radiotherapy at Douala General Hospital, in order to establish an up-to-date overview and contribute to improving the quality of care.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

A descriptive cross-sectional study with retrospective data collection was conducted in the radiotherapy department of the Douala General Hospital (HGD). The objective was to evaluate the survival of patients with non-metastatic nasopharyngeal carcinoma treated with radiotherapy. The inclusion period ran from 1 January 2017 to 31 December 2022. All patients, regardless of age or gender, with a histologically proven diagnosis of non-metastatic nasopharyngeal cancer (stages I to IVA

according to the AJCC 8th edition classification) and who had been treated with radiotherapy at the HGD during the study period were included. An essential criterion was to have a complete and usable medical record. Patients whose medical records were deemed unusable or incomplete (lack of information on stage, treatment or initial follow-up) were systematically excluded from the study. Patients who did not complete their prescribed radiotherapy protocol, those with a second concurrent or previous cancer, and those who refused to participate in follow-up telephone interviews were also excluded from the study.

Sampling was consecutive and exhaustive over the defined period. Information was collected using a standardised, pre-tested technical data sheet. This collection took place in two main phases. The first phase involved retrospective data collection, which consisted of examining medical records in the archives of the radiotherapy department at Douala General Hospital, the oncology department at Yaoundé General Hospital, and the oncology department at Laquintinie Hospital in Douala. The data collected covered sociodemographic characteristics (age, gender, occupation, place of residence, etc.), clinical characteristics of the disease (clinical presentation, TNM stage according to the AJCC 8th edition, histological type, etc.), the treatment modalities received (radiotherapy dose, radiotherapy schedule, protocol and number of courses of the various chemotherapies received (concomitant, neoadjuvant, adjuvant, etc.) and initial data on post-radiotherapy progression.

The second phase involved gathering additional information and follow-up. This consisted of conducting telephone interviews with patients (or their relatives) who did not continue their treatment at the three oncology centres after radiotherapy. The aim here was to obtain accurate and up-to-date information on their state of health and any events (recurrence, death, complications) beyond the last consultation date recorded in their radiotherapy department file.

In the study, censored patients were defined as those whose last documented contact was that of a living patient but who were lost to follow-up at some point during the follow-up period without it being possible to determine their vital status (alive or deceased) at the end of the study. For the analysis of overall survival (OS), the initial event was the date of histological diagnosis of cavum cancer and the final event was death from any cause or censoring. For the analysis of recurrence-free survival (RFS), the initial event was the date of the first post-treatment evaluation confirming a complete response, and the final event was the occurrence of locoregional or distant recurrence, death (from any cause), or censoring, whichever occurred first.

Data analysis was performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 22.0. Survival probabilities were estimated using the Kaplan-Meier method. Potential prognostic factors were identified using Cox regression models, first in univariate analysis, then in multivariate analysis to identify independent determinants of OS and SSR survival.

This research was submitted to and received ethical approval from the Institutional Ethics and Research Committee (CIER) of the Faculty of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences (FMSB) of the University of Yaoundé 1. The necessary administrative authorisations for access to the files were obtained from the management of the General Hospital of Douala, the General Hospital of Yaoundé and the Laquintinie Hospital of Douala. The oral consent of the patients or their legal representatives was obtained before the telephone interviews were conducted, thus ensuring the protection of their rights. The anonymity and confidentiality of patient data were rigorously guaranteed throughout the study.

RESULTS

We initially identified 183 cases of patients treated with radiotherapy for non-metastatic cavum cancer at Douala General Hospital between 2017 and 2022. After evaluating the eligibility criteria, 75 cases were definitively selected for this analysis.

Patient Socio demographic profile

The patients' ages ranged from 12 to 74 years, with a mean age of 42.4 ± 16.2 years. The majority of the cohort belonged to the 35-65 age group (60%), followed by the 18-35 age group (26.7%). Patients over 65 and those under 18 accounted for 9.3% and 4% of the series, respectively (Table I).

Table I. Treatment characteristics of patients with non-metastatic nasopharyngeal cancer (N=75)

Variable	N	%
Radiotherapy		
Total dose (Gy)		
[40-60[5	6.7
[60-66]	70	93.3
Treatment duration (days)		
<45	5	6.7
[45-60[32	42.7
≥60	38	50.7
Concurrent chemotherapy		
Number of cycles		
0	3	4.0
1-3	16	21.3
≥4	56	74.7
Protocols		
CDDP	71	94.7
Other	4	5.3
Induction chemotherapy		
Number of cycles		
0	5	6.7
1-3	47	62.7
≥4	23	30.7
Adjuvant chemotherapy		
Number of cycles		
0	64	85.3
1-3	1	1.3
≥4	10	13.3
Palliative chemotherapy		
Number of cycles		
0	58	77.3
≥4	17	22.7

The population was predominantly male (62.7%), with a

sex ratio of 1.68. In terms of place of residence, 49 patients lived in large cities (Douala and Yaoundé) compared to 26 patients from other urban or rural areas. The socio-professional category of entrepreneurs and

self-employed workers was the most represented (41.3%), with the other categories being retirees (24%), unemployed and salaried workers (18.7% each), and pupils/students (16%).

Figure 1. Kaplan-Meier curve for overall survival

Figure 2. Kaplan-Meier curve for disease free survival

Clinical presentation

Patients were symptomatic in 93.3% of cases at diagnosis. The predominant symptoms were rhinological manifestations (46.7%), followed by otological symptoms (36%) and cervical lymphadenopathy

(30.7%). Ophthalmological and neurological involvement was rare (4%). The most common histological type was WHO Type III (57%), confirming the predominance of undifferentiated carcinoma, followed by Type II (40%) and Type I (3%). In the vast majority of cases, the diagnosis was made at locally advanced stages: stage III accounted for 57.3% of cases,

followed by stages IV (20%) and II (20%). Stage I was found in only 1.3% of patients.

Table II. Factors associated with recurrence-free survival (Cox multivariate analysis)

Sociodemographic profile	Recurrence-free survival N(%)		HR ¹	95% CI ²	p-value
	Yes (n=57)	No (n=18)			
Age (years)					
[35-65[33 (73.3)	12 (26.7)	Ref	Ref	
[18-35[15 (75.0)	5 (25.0)	-	-	0.994
>65	7 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	14.7	[5.04-42.6]	<0.001
<18	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	0.88	[0.21-3.73]	0.860
Sex					
Male	35 (74.5)	12 (25.5)	Ref	Ref	
Female	22 (78.6)	6 (21.4)	1.06	[0.61-1.84]	0.828

¹HR = Hazard Ratio; ²CI = Confidence Interval

Table III. Factors associated with overall survival (Cox multivariate analysis)

Sociodemographic profile	Death N(%)		HR ¹	95% CI ²	p-value
	Yes (n=28)	No (n=47)			
Age (years)					
[35-65[19 (42.2)	26 (57.8)	Ref	Ref	
[18-35[4 (20.0)	16 (80.0)	0.25	[0.08-0.79]	0.018
>65	4 (57.1)	3 (42.9)	5.18	[1.58-17.0]	0.007
<18	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)	0.22	[0.02-1.95]	0.174
Sex					
Male	16 (34.0)	31 (66.0)	Ref	Ref	
Female	12 (42.9)	16 (57.1)	1.57	[0.73-3.38]	0.249

¹HR = Hazard Ratio; ²CI = Confidence Interval

Treatment features

External radiotherapy was the mainstay of treatment. Doses ranged from 40 to 66 Gy to the cavum and bilateral cervical lymph node areas, using a sequential irradiation technique with programmed volume reduction, with an average interval of 14 days between the two sequences. This radiotherapy was combined with weekly concomitant platinum-based chemotherapy in 96% of cases. Combination with induction chemotherapy was observed in 92.7% of cases, with adjuvant chemotherapy in 14.6% of cases, and with palliative chemotherapy in 22.7% of cases. (Table I summarises all the therapeutic modalities).

Response to treatment and survival

Post-treatment assessment was generally performed using cervical, thoracic, abdominal and pelvic CT scans and nasofibroscope, mostly after more than 3 months (53.3%) or at 3 months (41.3%). After treatment completion, good local control of the disease was achieved in 66 patients (88%). Partial control was observed in 4 patients, with the response unknown in 5 patients.

Overall survival (OS)

At the end of the investigations, 16 patients (21.6%) were declared definitively lost to follow-up and censored. The Kaplan-Meier curve for overall survival (OS) shows a median survival of approximately 25 months. The probability of survival remains very high during the first 14 months, but drops dramatically between the 15th and 38th months, stabilising at around

5% from the 50th month onwards. The probability of overall survival was 90% at 12 months, 40% at 24 months, 18% at 36 months and 5% at 60 months. (Figure 1)

Disease free survival (DFS)

The median recurrence-free survival (RFS) was 23 months. The probability of RFS is high during the first 10 months, then decreases between the 12th and 25th months, stabilising at 4% from the 38th month onwards. The probabilities of recurrence-free survival were 90% at 12 months, 36% at 24 months, 6% at 36 months, and 4% at 60 months (Figure 2).

Factors associated with survival

Factors associated with disease free survival (DFS)

Multivariate analysis identified age over 65 as an independent risk factor significantly associated with poor recurrence-free survival. The hazard ratio (HR) was 14.7 (95% confidence interval [5.04-42.6], $p < 0.001$) (Table 2).

Factors associated with overall survival (OS)

Age emerged as a major prognostic determinant of overall survival. The age group over 65 was associated with poor overall survival, while the age group 18 to 35 was associated with better overall survival (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

Epidemiological and clinical characteristics

The sociodemographic characteristics of our study population, with a median age of 42.4±16.2 years and a predominance of males (sex ratio of 1.68), are consistent with the data reported by Engbang et al. in Cameroon [5]

and OuYang et al. in China [10], confirming the classic epidemiological profile of nasopharyngeal carcinoma. Regarding initial symptoms, our series revealed a decreasing frequency of rhinological (46.7%), lymph node (36%), otological (30.7%) and ophthalmological (4%) symptoms. This profile differs from that of Engbang et al. [5], which highlighted the predominance of lymph node symptoms (82.5%). This discrepancy could be attributed to the exclusion of metastatic stages in our study and the frequent use of neoadjuvant chemotherapy prior to referral to the radiotherapy department. The histology was predominantly WHO type III, in line with the observations of Mouelle et al. [6] and international data for non-Caucasian populations [11]. The predominance of locally advanced stages (stages III and IVA) at admission is a recurring finding in Cameroon [5; 6]. This late diagnosis is likely to be multifactorial, involving a limiting socio-economic context and dysfunctions in the healthcare system that delay referral to specialised centres.

Therapeutic approaches and compliance with international standards

The standard curative radiotherapy protocol at Douala General Hospital is divided into two stages, delivering a total dose of 66 Gy (40 Gy/20 fractions over a large volume, followed by 26 Gy/13 fractions over a reduced volume). This protocol, applied to 93.3% of patients, is distinguished by an average 14-day break between the two sequences. This extension of the overall treatment time (average of 59.11 ± 11.5 days) is not in line with the recommendations of learned societies [7; 13], which highlight the negative impact of prolonged treatment time on local control, possibly through accelerated tumour repopulation. Concomitant weekly cisplatin-based chemotherapy (40 mg/m²) was administered to 96% of patients (74.7% receiving ≥ 4 courses), which is similar to the results of Alami et al. in Morocco [12] and in line with the ESMO-EURACAN guidelines for advanced stages (stages $\geq T2$) [7]. Furthermore, the use of induction chemotherapy (93.3%) and adjuvant chemotherapy (14.7%) for these locally advanced stages is also in line with ESMO recommendations [7; 14].

Prognosis and survival analysis

The complete clinical response rate of 61.3% in our series, although comparable to previous data from Mouelle et al. (1990-1996) in the same institution [6], is significantly lower than those reported by other international centres such as the Hassan II University Hospital Centre (CHU) [12]. This poor local control can be attributed to a combination of adverse prognostic factors, including the high prevalence of advanced stages (III, IVA) and the use of conventional two-dimensional radiotherapy (2D-RT) [5; 6; 9], a technique that limits cancer dose escalation and optimisation of target volume coverage compared to modern techniques (IMRT). Survival data are concerning. Overall 5-year survival is only 9.3%. This rate is significantly lower than those observed in high-income countries such as Singapore (1992-1994) and the United States (2009-2015) [7; 15]. Similarly, 5-year recurrence-free survival is 5.3%, which is very low compared to European benchmarks [7]. This

survival gap is multifactorial, involving the predominance of advanced stages, the inherent limitations of 2D RT technology and, potentially, the negative impact of the therapeutic break in the local radiotherapy protocol. A high rate of loss to follow-up (22.67% censored) potentially biases the survival estimate. This phenomenon could reflect poor adherence to local follow-up. A high rate of loss to follow-up (22.67% censored) potentially biases the survival estimate. This phenomenon could reflect poor adherence to post-treatment follow-up. This phenomenon could reflect poor adherence to post-treatment follow-up, malfunctions in archiving, or a flawed data collection system.

Prognostic factors

Age emerged as the only significant prognostic factor. Belonging to the >65 age group was associated with an increased risk of poor overall survival (HR=5.18; CI[1.58–17.0]; $p<0.007$) and poor recurrence-free survival (HR=14.7; CI [5.04–42.6]; $p<0.001$). Conversely, the 18–35 age group was associated with better overall survival (HR=0.25; CI [0.08–0.79]; $p<0.015$). These results are consistent with those of Bossi et al. [7], who reported a better 5-year survival rate in younger patients (15–45 years: 72%) compared to older patients (65–74 years: 36%). However, it is crucial to contextualise these data in terms of life expectancy in Cameroon (estimated at 61.8 years in 2021) and the increased prevalence of comorbidities in older subjects [16]. Contrary to data in the literature [5; 7; 15], no significant link was established between survival and other classic factors (T stage, N stage, neoadjuvant chemotherapy). This lack of correlation is probably due to the limited sample size and the high rate of patients lost to follow-up, which reduce the statistical power of the analysis.

CONCLUSION

Patients treated for non-metastatic nasopharyngeal cancer had a mean age of 42.4 ± 16.2 years. The majority of cases were locally advanced (stages III and IVA) and histologically classified as WHO type III (UCNT). The predominant treatment regimen included concomitant chemoradiotherapy in 96% of patients, mostly preceded by neoadjuvant chemotherapy (93.3%). The complete response rate was 61.3%. However, prognostic analysis reveals concerning survival rates. Overall survival was 37.3% at 1 year and 9.3% at 5 years. Similarly, recurrence-free survival was 24% at 1 year and fell to 5.3% at 5 years. These data suggest that the management of locally advanced stages is still suboptimal in this hospital. Univariate analysis identified age as the only significant prognostic factor. More specifically, patients in the 18–45 age group had better overall survival, while patients over 65 years of age were associated with significantly lower overall survival and recurrence-free survival. These results highlight the importance of age in tumour aggressiveness and therapeutic tolerance. Further efforts are needed to improve these survival rates, in particular by optimising treatment protocols and providing early care for patients.

Study Limit

It is imperative to consider the methodological limitations inherent in this retrospective study, which could influence the interpretation of the results and their clinical significance. Firstly, the small sample size limits the statistical power of our analysis. Consequently, caution should be exercised when generalising the conclusions regarding survival rates and prognostic factors identified to the wider Cameroonian population of nasopharyngeal cancer patients. Secondly, the retrospective nature of data collection led to gaps. We encountered varying degrees of completeness in medical records, resulting in a lack of detailed information on certain staging or follow-up assessments. This incompleteness could potentially bias the accurate assessment of initial staging and therapeutic response. Finally, limiting recruitment to three oncology departments (Douala General Hospital, Yaoundé General Hospital and Laquintinie Hospital in Douala) was a major obstacle, resulting in a significant number of patients being lost to follow-up. This limitation in longitudinal follow-up compromises the accuracy of long-term survival estimates and could mask important prognostic factors that were not identified due to a lack of complete data.

DECLARATIONS**Acknowledgements**

We sincerely thank all those who made this study possible.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

The work was carried out with own funds.

Ethical considerations

All stages of the work were carried out in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki. The approval of the institutional ethics committee was obtained prior to the start of the study. This work did not involve any experimentation on humans or animals and it does not contain any personal information that could identify the patients

Data availability

Data is available on reasonable request from the principal author.

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